

Class	Species Name	Length (bp)	Rebase Best Match	Pairwise Identity (%)
<i>Actinopterygii</i>	<i>Sphaeramia orbicularis</i>	2921	hAT-1_SSa (<i>Salmo salar</i>)	81
	<i>Xiphophorus hellerii</i>	3231	hAT-1_XT (<i>Xenopus tropicalis</i>)	79
	<i>Archocentrus centrarchus</i>	2522	hAT-2_PM (<i>Petromyzon marinus</i>)	83
	<i>Takifugu rubripes</i>	2612	hAT-7_PM (<i>Petromyzon marinus</i>)	82
	<i>Erpetoichthys calabaricus</i>	2591	hAT-4_SSa (<i>Salmo salar</i>)	88
	<i>Oryzias latipes</i>	2614	hAT-1_SSa (<i>Salmo salar</i>)	67
	<i>Xiphophorus couchianus</i>	2756	hAT-1_SSa (<i>Salmo salar</i>)	75
	<i>Gouania willdenowi</i>	2789	CHAPLIN4_FR (<i>Takifugu rubripes</i>)	91
	<i>Cottoperca gobio</i>	2656	hAT-1_SSa (<i>Salmo salar</i>)	74
	<i>Kryptolebias marmoratus</i>	2673	hAT-1_SSa (<i>Salmo salar</i>)	74
	<i>Larimichthys crocea</i>	2787	hAT-6_XT (<i>Xenopus tropicalis</i>)	87
	<i>Chelmon rostratus</i>	2530	hAT-1_SSa (<i>Salmo salar</i>)	80
	<i>Maylandia zebra</i>	2551	hAT-1_SSa (<i>Salmo salar</i>)	87
	<i>Salvelinus namaycush</i>	2488	hAT-1_SSa (<i>Salmo salar</i>)	99
	<i>Oncorhynchus kisutch</i>	2508	hAT-1_SSa (<i>Salmo salar</i>)	98
	<i>Salmo trutta</i>	2893	hAT-1_SSa (<i>Salmo salar</i>)	99
	<i>Labrus bergylta</i>	2191	hAT-2B_PM (<i>Petromyzon marinus</i>)	96
	<i>Labeo rohita</i>	2528	hAT-8_PM (<i>Petromyzon marinus</i>)	72
	<i>Paralichthys olivaceus</i>	2255	hAT-17_SSa (<i>Salmo salar</i>)	79
	<i>Gadus morhua</i>	2803	hAT-22_DR (<i>Danio rerio</i>)	70
	<i>Lates calcarifer</i>	2788	hAT-9_DR (<i>Danio rerio</i>)	83
	<i>Collichthys lucidus</i>	3127	CHAPLIN8_FR (<i>Takifugu rubripes</i>)	91
	<i>Anguilla anguilla</i>	3562	hAT-1_SSa (<i>Salmo salar</i>)	95
<i>Perca flavescens</i>	2442	hAT-1_SSa (<i>Salmo salar</i>)	80	
<i>Parambassis ranga</i>	2630	hAT-4_SSa (<i>Salmo salar</i>)	70	
<i>Amphibia</i>	<i>Bufo bufo</i>	2392	hAT-1_SSa (<i>Salmo salar</i>)	93
<i>Reptilia</i>	<i>Anolis carolinensis</i>	2250	hAT-2_AC (<i>Anolis carolinensis</i>)	100
	<i>Alligator mississippiensis</i>	4120	hAT-7_AMi (<i>Alligator mississippiensis</i>)	87

Table S2: Species from the *Actinopterygii*, *Reptilia* and *Amphibia* class containing hAT transposons that were incorrectly annotated as GTF2IRD2/2A. The best match of each hAT transposon to the Rebase database and the corresponding pairwise identity is shown.

Table S3: 3' and 5' TIRs of TEs misannotated as GTF2IRD2/2A

3_TIR	5_TIR	
>Sphaeramia_orbicularis	>Sphaeramia_orbicularis	
AGTTTGACACCCCTG	CACATATGTCAAAC	
>Xiphophorus_hellerii	>Xiphophorus_hellerii	
AGTTTGACACCCCTG	CCAGTGTATTGATGT	
>Archocentrus_centrarchus	>Archocentrus_centrarchus	
AGTTTGGACACCCCTG	CAGGGGTGTCCAAAC	
>Takifugu_rubripes	>Takifugu_rubripes	
AGTTTGCCCATGCCT	CAGGGGTGGGCAAAC	
>Erpetoichthys_calabaricus	>Erpetoichthys_calabaricus	
TATAAGCCTTGCTTG	CACAGGTGTCAAAC	
>Oryzias_latipes	>Oryzias_latipes	
AATTGCCACCCCTG	CAGACCTGGGCAAAC	
>Xiphophorus_couchianus	>Xiphophorus_couchianus	
ACTTTGACACCCCTG	CACATATGTCAGAGT	
>Gouania_willdenowi	>Gouania_willdenowi	
AGTTTGACACCCCTG	CAGGGGTGTCAAACG	
>Cottoperca_gobio	>Cottoperca_gobio	
ACTTTGACACCCCTG	CACATATGTCAGAGT	
>Kryptolebias_marmoratus	>Kryptolebias_marmoratus	
ACTTTGACACCCCTG	CACATATGTCAGAGT	
>Larimichthys_crocea	>Larimichthys_crocea	
TAAAGAACCCAGCTA	CATATGTGTCAAAC	
>Chelmon_rostratus	>Chelmon_rostratus	
AGTTTGACACCCCTG	CATATGAGTCAAAC	
>Maylandia_zebra	>Maylandia_zebra	
AGTTTGACACCTATG	CAGGGGTGTCAAAC	
>Salvelinus_namaycush	>Salvelinus_namaycush	
AGTTTGACACCCCTG	CATGGGTGTCAAAC	
>Oncorhynchus_kisutch	>Oncorhynchus_kisutch	
AGTTTGACACCCCTG	CATGGGTGTCAAAC	
>Salmo_trutta	>Salmo_trutta	
AGTTTGACACCCCTG	CATGGGTGTCAAAC	
>Labrus_bergylta	>Labrus_bergylta	
AGTTTGGACACCCCT	CAGGGGTGTCCAAAG	
>Labeo_rohita	>Labeo_rohita	
AGTTTGAGACCCCTG	CAGGGGTCTCAAAC	
>Acipenser_ruthenus	>Acipenser_ruthenus	
TATTGACTACCCCTG	CAGGGATAGTCAATT	
>Paralichthys_olivaceus	>Paralichthys_olivaceus	
AGGTTCCCCACCCCT	CAGGGGTGGGGAACG	
>Gadus_morhua	>Gadus_morhua	
AATGGGGCTGCCCTG	CAGGGGTGCCCAAAT	
>Lates_calcarifer	>Lates_calcarifer	
AAGTTTGGGGACCCC	AGTGGTCCCCAAAC	

>Collichthys_lucidus	>Collichthys_lucidus	
AGTTTGAGACCCCTG	CAGGGGTCTCAAAC	
>Anguilla_anguilla	>Anguilla_anguilla	
AGATTGTAGCCCCTA	CAGGGGTGTCAAAC	
>Perca_flavescens	>Perca_flavescens	
AGTTTGACACCCTTG	CACATGTGTCAAAC	
>Parambassis_ranga	>Parambassis_ranga	
CAATGCCCAGGTCTG	CAGGGGTGGGCAATT	
>Bufo_bufo	>Bufo_bufo	
AGTTTGACACCTATG	CAGGGGTGTCAAAC	
>Anolis_carolinensis	>Anolis_carolinensis	
AGTTTGGGGACCCCTG	TCAGGGGTGCTTTGAT	
>Alligator_mississippiensis	>Alligator_mississippiensis	
AATTGCCCACCCTG	AGCAGGGTGGGCAAAA	

Species name	5' TIR	[hAT-6]	3' TIR
<i>Sphaeramia orbicularis</i>	-CACATATGT CAAAC -T-	-----	AGTTT GAC ACCCTG
<i>Xiphophorus hellerii</i>	-CCAGTGTATTGATG-T-	-----	AGTTT GAC ACCCTG
<i>Archocentrus centrarchus</i>	-CAGGGGTGT CCAAA -C-	-----	AGTTT GGAC ACCCTG
<i>Takifugu rubripes</i>	-CAGGGGTGGG CAAA -C-	-----	AGTTT GCCCATGC CT-
<i>Erpetoichthys calabaricus</i>	-CACAGGTGT CAAAC -T-	-----	TATAAGCCTTG CTTG
<i>Oryzias latipes</i>	-CAGACCTGGG CAAA -C-	-----	AATTGCC CAACCCTG
<i>Xiphophorus couchianus</i>	-CACATATGT CAGAG -T-	-----	ACTTTGAC ACCCTG
<i>Gouania willdenowi</i>	-CAGGGGTGT CAAAC -G-	-----	AGTTT GAC ACCCTG
<i>Cottoperca gobio</i>	-CACATATGT CAGAG -T-	-----	ACTTTGAC ACCCTG
<i>Kryptolebias marmoratus</i>	-CACATATGT CAGAG -T-	-----	ACTTTGAC ACCCTG
<i>Larimichthys crocea</i>	-CATATGTGT CAAAC -T-	-----	TAAAGAACC CAGCTA
<i>Chelmon rostratus</i>	-CATATGAGT CAAAC -T-	-----	AGTTT GAC ACCCTG
<i>Maylandia zebra</i>	-CAGGGGTGT CAAAC -T-	-----	AGTTT GACAC CTATG
<i>Salvelinus namaycush</i>	-CATGGGTGT CAAAC -T-	-----	GATTTGAC ACCCTG
<i>Oncorhynchus kisutch</i>	-CATGGGTGT CAAAC -T-	-----	AGTTT GAC ACCCTG
<i>Salmo trutta</i>	-CATGGGTGT CAAAC -T-	-----	AGTTT GAC ACCCTG
<i>Labrus bergylta</i>	-CAGGGGTGT CCAAA -G-	-----	AGTTT GGAC ACCCT-
<i>Labeo rohita</i>	-CAGGGGTCT CAAAC -T-	-----	AGTTT GAG ACCCTG
<i>Acipenser ruthenus</i>	-CAGGGATAGT CAAT -T-	-----	TATTGACT ACCCTG
<i>Paralichthys olivaceus</i>	-CAGGGGTGGG GAAC -G-	-----	AGTT CCCCACCCT-
<i>Gadus morhua</i>	-CAGGGGTG CCCCAAA -T-	-----	AATGGGCTG CCCTG
<i>Lates calcarifer</i>	--AGTGGT CCCCAACT -----	-----	AAGTTTGGG GACCCC--
<i>Collichthys lucidus</i>	-CAGGGGTCT CAAAC -T-	-----	AGTTT GAG ACCCTG
<i>Anguilla anguilla</i>	-CAGGGGTGT CAAAC -T-	-----	AGATTGTAG CCCCTA
<i>Perca flavescens</i>	-CACATGTGT CAAAC -T-	-----	AGTTT GACAC CCCTG
<i>Parambassis ranga</i>	-CAGGGGTGGG CAAT -T-	-----	CAATGCC CAGGTCTG
<i>Bufo bufo</i>	-CAGGGGTGT CAAAC -T-	-----	AGTTT GACAC CTATG
<i>Anolis carolinensis</i>	TCAGGGGTGCTTT GA -T-	-----	AGTTT GGG GACCCTG
<i>Alligator mississippiensis</i>	AG CAGGGTGGGCAAA -A-	-----	AATTGCC CAACCCTG

Table S4: Multiple alignment of the 5' and 3' TIRs of *Actinopterygii*, *Amphibia* and *Reptilia* hAT transposons derived from sequences misannotated as GTF2IRD2/2A. Nucleotides in bold text are conserved in most of the species.

Species Name	Predicted Sequence	Rebase Best Match	Frequency
<i>Danio rerio</i>	Zinc finger BED domain-containing protein 1-like (ZBED1)	hAT-30_DR	1
	Ribosome-binding protein 1-like	MSAT-3_DR	1
	Uncharacterized	Helitron-3_DR ISL2EU-1_DR	13
<i>Thamnophis sirtalis</i>	General transcription factor II-I repeat domain-containing protein 2-like	hAT-11_CPB	1
	Zinc finger, BED-type containing 4 (ZBED4)	hAT-6_DR	3
<i>Anolis carolinensis</i>	Uncharacterized	Neptune-3_ACar	4
<i>Xenopus tropicalis</i>	Fibroin heavy chain-like	Helitron-N4_AmRa	1
	Coiled-coil domain containing 51 (ccdc51)	Kolobok-2_XT	4
	Uncharacterized	BEL-10_XT-I Polinton-2_XT Kolobok-1_XT	13
<i>Gallus gallus</i>	Uncharacterized	ERV2-10_GG-I	3

Table S5: A sample of TEs from vertebrates which were incorrectly annotated as various other proteins and uncharacterised loci. The best TE match in Repbase was found for each predicted sequence. Frequency refers to the number of times the predicted sequence overlapped with a TE from the top 25 hits for each species.

Table S7: Sample of misannotation events

Species Name/GenBank assembly ID	Gene ID	Chromosome	Gene Coordinates	Gene description	TE overlap coordinates	TE match	100% overlapped TEs (excluding simple repeats):Total protein-coding gene count
Garter Snake/GCA_001077635.2							
Oldhat1 (hAT-6_DR)	XM_014072166.1_cds_2_0_NW_013660042v1_65137_f	Scaffold2362	65136-68622	Thamnomphis sirtalis zinc finger, BED-type containing 4 (ZBED4), transcript variant X2, mRNA	67656-67826	hAT-6_DR	0.0010
Oldhat1 (hAT-6_DR)	XM_014072166.1_cds_2_0_NW_013660042v1_65137_f	Scaffold2362	65136-68622	Thamnomphis sirtalis zinc finger, BED-type containing 4 (ZBED4), transcript variant X1, mRNA	67656-67826	hAT-6_DR	
hAT-16_Crp	XM_014064415.1_cds_1_0_NW_01365862v1_52202_f	Scaffold982	52201-54022	Thamnomphis sirtalis general transcription factor II-I repeat domain-containing protein 2-like (LOC106547299), mRNA	52765-53985	HAT3_MD	
hAT-16_Crp	XM_014074848.1_cds_0_0_NW_013661234v1_33330_r	Scaffold3554	33329-35276, 35102-35206	Thamnomphis sirtalis uncharacterized LOC106555913 (LOC106555913), mRNA	34045-34308	HAT3_MD	
hAT-16_Crp	XM_014065111.1_cds_5_0_NW_01365873v1_257195_r	Scaffold1057	258093-258145	Thamnomphis sirtalis general transcription factor II-I repeat domain-containing protein 2-like (LOC106547845), mRNA	257154-258998	hAT-11_CPaB	
Gypsy-5_AMI-I	XM_014074749.1_cds_6_0_NW_013661182v1_21107_f	Scaffold3502	21106-21704	Thamnomphis sirtalis uncharacterized LOC106555836 (LOC106555836), mRNA	21126-21687	Gypsy-3_LaAg-I	
Gypsy-5_AMI-I	XM_014055008.1_cds_1_0_NW_013657942v1_659303_r	Scaffold262	659302-661390	Thamnomphis sirtalis uncharacterized protein K02A2.6-like (LOC106540031), mRNA	659985-660347	Gypsy-3_LaAg-I	
Gypsy-5_AMI-I	XM_014056889.1_cds_1_0_NW_013658158v1_231451_f	Scaffold478	231702-231894, 233747-233793	Thamnomphis sirtalis uncharacterized protein K02A2.6-like (LOC106542846), mRNA	231450-231911, 233771-234788	Gypsy-3_LaAg-I	
Gypsy-5_AMI-I	XM_014056157.1_cds_2_0_NW_013658010v1_791275_f	Scaffold321	792851-792982	Thamnomphis sirtalis uncharacterized protein K02A2.6-like (LOC106540872), mRNA	791274-793709	Gypsy-3_LaAg-I	
Gypsy-5_AMI-I	XM_014057610.1_cds_4_0_NW_013658085v1_131307_r	Scaffold405	131861-131941	Thamnomphis sirtalis uncharacterized LOC106542012 (LOC106542012), mRNA	131306-132086	Gypsy-3_LaAg-I	
Lizard/GCA_00090745.2							
Neptune1_Ac	XM_016991679.1_cds_1_0_chr2_184740785_r	2	184740784-184741767	Anolis carolinensis uncharacterized LOC107982479 (LOC107982479), mRNA	184741259-184741383	Neptune-3_ACar	0.0022
Neptune1_Ac	XM_008108518.2_cds_0_0_chr4_2987135v1_f	4	29871375-29871876	Anolis carolinensis uncharacterized LOC103278512 (LOC103278512), mRNA	29871352-29872654	Neptune-3_ACar	
Neptune1_Ac	XM_016996278.1_cds_1_0_chrUn_GL3_43299_678979_r	Uncharacterised	679309-679413	Anolis carolinensis uncharacterized LOC107983282 (LOC107983282), mRNA	678978-680031	Neptune-3_ACar	
Neptune1_Ac	XM_016996337.1_cds_1_0_chrUn_GL3_43309_1013021_f	Uncharacterised	1013262-1013323	Anolis carolinensis uncharacterized LOC107983290 (LOC107983290), mRNA	1013020-1013351	Neptune-3_ACar	
Western clawed frog/GCF_001663975.1							
BEL-4-1_XT	XM_031899399.1_cds_1_0_chr3_135678301_f	3	135678300-135684231	Xenopus tropicalis uncharacterized LOC116409808 (LOC116409808), transcript variant X3, mRNA	135678378-135678542, 135679094-135684200	BEL-10_XT-I	0.0086
BEL-2-1_XT	XM_004912313.3_cds_1_0_chr4_79669121_f	4	79669120-79673593	Xenopus tropicalis uncharacterized LOC101731929 (LOC101731929), transcript variant X1, mRNA	79669291-79673549	BEL-13_XT-LTR	
Pointon-2_XT	XM_031898444.1_cds_1_0_chr3_2131755_f	3	2131754-2136857	Xenopus tropicalis uncharacterized LOC116409665 (LOC116409665), mRNA	2132200-2136890	Pointon-2_XT	
BEL-4-1_XT	XM_031897261.1_cds_1_0_chr2_15675193v1_f	2	156755134-156759487	Xenopus tropicalis uncharacterized LOC101730439 (LOC101730439), transcript variant X1, mRNA	156755218-156758893, 156759245-156759409	BEL-10_XT-I	
BEL-4-1_XT	XM_031893963.1_cds_1_0_chr9_7020578_f	9	7020577-7024930	Xenopus tropicalis uncharacterized LOC101730954 (LOC101730954), mRNA	7020655-7020819, 7021371-7024846	BEL-10_XT-I	
BEL-4-1_XT	XM_031891904.1_cds_1_0_chr8_123361984_r	8	123361983-123365880	Xenopus tropicalis uncharacterized LOC116406890 (LOC116406890), transcript variant X3, mRNA	123362173-123365086, 123365638-123365802	BEL-10_XT-I	
Oldhat1	XM_004919553.4_cds_1_0_chr6_6446974_r	6	6446973-6450126	Xenopus tropicalis ZBED6 C-terminal like (zbed6l), mRNA	6446974-6448789, 6449084-6449229	hAT-4_LCh	
BEL-4-1_XT	XM_031903497.1_cds_0_0_chr6_60126639_f	6	60126638-60129632	Xenopus tropicalis uncharacterized LOC116411480 (LOC116411480), mRNA	60127403-60129036, 60129050-60129469	BEL-10_XT-I	
BEL-4-1_XT	XM_031902948.1_cds_0_0_chr5_4581946v1_f	5	45814945-45818155	Xenopus tropicalis uncharacterized LOC116411075 (LOC116411075), mRNA	45815034-45816476, 45817112-45817431, 45817803-45817875	BEL-12_XT-I	
hAT-N13_XT	XM_031904473.1_cds_0_0_chr1_18003320v1_f	1	18003319-18004792	Xenopus tropicalis fibron heavy chain-like (LOC116411690), mRNA	18003321-18004761	Helitron-N4_AmRa	
BEL-4-1_XT	XM_031903613.1_cds_1_0_chr6_15119739_r	6	151119738-151125843	Xenopus tropicalis uncharacterized LOC116411480 (LOC116411480), mRNA	151120018-151120090, 151120462-151120781, 151121425-151122859	BEL-12_XT-I	
Kolobok-1_XT	XM_002939351.5_cds_1_0_chr4_14364162v1_f	4	143641620-143643918	Xenopus tropicalis uncharacterized LOC100487738 (LOC100487738), mRNA	143642514-143643824	Kolobok-2_XT	
Kolobok-2_XT	XM_012960629.3_cds_2_0_chr4_139436205_r	4	139436204-139438373	Xenopus tropicalis coiled-coil domain containing 51 (ccdc51), transcript variant X2, mRNA	139436439-139437619, 139437864-139438373	Kolobok-2_XT	
Kolobok-2_XT	XM_012960632.3_cds_3_0_chr4_139436205_r	4	139436204-139438373	Xenopus tropicalis coiled-coil domain containing 51 (ccdc51), transcript variant X4, mRNA	139436439-139437619, 139437864-139438373	Kolobok-2_XT	
Kolobok-2_XT	XM_031899861.1_cds_1_0_chr4_139445785_r	4	139445784-139447953	Xenopus tropicalis coiled-coil domain containing 51 (ccdc51), transcript variant X1, mRNA	139446059-139447189	Kolobok-2_XT	
Kolobok-2_XT	XM_012960631.3_cds_2_0_chr4_139445785_r	4	139445784-139447953	Xenopus tropicalis coiled-coil domain containing 51 (ccdc51), transcript variant X5, mRNA	139446059-139447189, 139447448-139447953	Kolobok-2_XT	
Kolobok-2_XT	XM_012960630.3_cds_2_0_chr4_139445785_r	4	139445784-139447953	Xenopus tropicalis coiled-coil domain containing 51 (ccdc51), transcript variant X3, mRNA	139446059-139447189, 139447448-139447953	Kolobok-2_XT	
ERV1-4-1_XT	XM_031893987.1_cds_1_0_chr1_18637452v1_f	1	186374828-186376040	Xenopus tropicalis uncharacterized LOC116407911 (LOC116407911), transcript variant X1, mRNA	186374940-186376032	ERV1-4-LTR_XT	
Kolobok-1_XT	XM_031899558.1_cds_1_0_chr3_146989328_r	3	146989327-146991580	Xenopus tropicalis uncharacterized LOC100489710 (LOC100489710), mRNA	146989633-146990593, 146991298-146991580	Kolobok-1_XT	
BEL-4-1_XT	XM_031906411.1_cds_1_0_chr7_19665528v1_f	7	19665527-19671491	Xenopus tropicalis uncharacterized LOC101733728 (LOC101733728), mRNA	19668370-19669238, 19669512-19669812, 19670448-19670767, 19671139-19671211	BEL-12_XT-I	
hAT-10_XT	XM_031893344.1_cds_1_0_chr9_5116818_r	9	5116817-5118084	Xenopus tropicalis repetitive proline-rich cell wall protein 2-like (LOC116407633), mRNA	5116862-5117198, 5117203-5118068	hAT-10_XT	
Zebrafish/GCA_00002035.4							
Helitron-2_DR	XM_02147356.1_cds_1_0_chr6_43353271v1_f	6	43353270-43361226	Danio rerio uncharacterized LOC101882029 (LOC101882029), mRNA	43355995-43361219, 43364165-43364347, 43365391-433653545	Helitron-3_DR	0.0123
Helitron-2_DR	XM_021477671.1_cds_1_0_chr7_6016929_r	7	6016928-6025151	Danio rerio uncharacterized LOC101884770 (LOC101884770), mRNA	6024876, 6025040	Helitron-3_DR	
Helitron-1_DR	XM_021474525.1_cds_3_0_chr4_31860679_f	4	31860678-31869702	Danio rerio uncharacterized LOC110439423 (LOC110439423), transcript variant X1, mRNA	31864431-31869631, 31863182-31863434	Helitron-4_DR	
Helitron-1_DR	XM_021475426.1_cds_2_0_chr4_31860679_f	4	31860678-31869702	Danio rerio uncharacterized LOC110439423 (LOC110439423), transcript variant X2, mRNA	31864431-31869631, 31863182-31863434	Helitron-4_DR	
Helitron-1_DR	XM_021479014.1_cds_2_0_chr9_44149090_r	9	44149089-44156601	Danio rerio uncharacterized LOC110440049 (LOC110440049), transcript variant X1, mRNA	44149812-44154310, 44155600-44156247	Helitron-4_DR	
Helitron-1_DR	XM_021479015.1_cds_3_0_chr9_44149090_r	9	44149089-44156601	Danio rerio uncharacterized LOC110440049 (LOC110440049), transcript variant X2, mRNA	44149812-44154310, 44155600-44156247	Helitron-4_DR	
IS4EU-2_DR	XM_009298353.3_cds_0_0_chrUn_KN1_50252v1_38179_f	Uncharacterised	38178-41307	Danio rerio uncharacterized protein K02A2.6-like (LOC103909980), mRNA	38229-41088	Gypsy-192_DR-I	
IS4EU-2_DR	XM_021468951.1_cds_1_0_chr21_2212889_r	21	2212888-2213916	Danio rerio uncharacterized LOC110437787 (LOC110437787), mRNA	2212925-2213779	ISL2EU-1_DR	
hAT-4_DR	XM_005155824.1_cds_0_0_chr11_17895941_f	11	17895940-17897068	Danio rerio zinc finger BED domain-containing protein 1-like (LOC101868897), mRNA	17895949-17896644	hAT-30_DR	
Helitron-1_DR	XM_021479014.1_cds_2_0_chr9_44149090_r	9	44149089-44156601	Danio rerio uncharacterized LOC110440049 (LOC110440049), transcript variant X1, mRNA	44149812-44154310	Helitron-4_DR	
Helitron-1_DR	XM_021479015.1_cds_3_0_chr9_44149090_r	9	44149089-44156601	Danio rerio uncharacterized LOC110440049 (LOC110440049), transcript variant X2, mRNA	44149812-44154310, 44155600-44156247	Helitron-4_DR	
IS4EU-2_DR	XM_009299506.3_cds_5_0_chr4_72375200_f	4	72375334-72375975	Danio rerio si:cabz01071907.1 (si:cabz01071907.1), transcript variant X1, mRNA	72375199-72376179	ISL2EU-1_DR	
IS4EU-2_DR	XM_021475290.1_cds_3_0_chr4_72375200_f	4	72375199-72376179	Danio rerio si:cabz01071907.1 (si:cabz01071907.1), transcript variant X2, mRNA	72375334-72375975	ISL2EU-1_DR	
IS4EU-2_DR	XM_021475289.1_cds_3_0_chr4_72375200_f	4	72375199-72376179	Danio rerio si:cabz01071907.1 (si:cabz01071907.1), transcript variant X2, mRNA	72375334-72375975	ISL2EU-1_DR	
Gypsy95-1_DR	XM_005173163.1_cds_0_0_chr14_21029570_f	14	21020569-21023734	Danio rerio uncharacterized protein K02A2.6-like (LOC101884733), mRNA	21022614-21023167, 21022028-21022217, 21021253-21021439	Gypsy-207_DR-I	
HATN16_DR	XM_009301735.3_cds_0_0_chr5_42276614_r	5	42276613-422778491	Danio rerio general transcription factor II-I repeat domain-containing protein 2-like (LOC103911071), mRNA	42277969-42778441	hAT-22_DR	
Gypsy158-1_DR	XM_017354380.1_cds_0_0_chrUn_KN1_50252v1_36860_f	Uncharacterised	36859-37786	Danio rerio uncharacterized LOC108182213 (LOC108182213), partial mRNA	36912-37375, 55085294-55085594, 55084659-55084824	Gypsy-192_DR-I	
MSAT-3_DR	XM_021466788.1_cds_1_0_chr16_55084565_r	16	55084564-55086621	Danio rerio ribosome-binding protein 1-like (LOC110437958), mRNA		MSAT-3_DR	
IS4EU-2_DR	XM_021473383.1_cds_3_0_chr20_K211_5614v1_all_44110_r	20	44109-45050	Danio rerio uncharacterized LOC110439056 (LOC110439056), mRNA	44236-44674	ISL2EU-1_DR	
IS4EU-2_DR	XM_002665730.6_cds_2_0_chr20_26894821_f	20	26894820-26895573	Danio rerio uncharacterized LOC100332023 (LOC100332023), mRNA	26894917-26895296	ISL2EU-2_DR	0.0035
Chicken/GCF_000002315.5							
GGERV28_L-int	XM_025144565.1_cds_0_0_chrW_1607037_f	W	1607036-1610930	Gallus gallus uncharacterized LOC112530482 (LOC112530482), mRNA	1607130-1607822, 1608104-1608480, 1608792-1610786	ERV2-10_GG-I	
GGLTR11-int	NM_001165913.1_cds_1_0_chr4_85934195v1_f	4	85934194-85938816	Gallus gallus uncharacterized LOC422926 (LOC422926), mRNA	85934448-85934643, 85935603-85935761, 85935829-85936719	ERV3-2_UCy-I	

Table S8: Conserved domains of GTF2IRD2/2A compared to TEs

#Batch	CD-search tool	NIH/NLM/NCBI	PSSM-ID	From	To	E-Value	Bitscore	Accession	Short name	Incomplete	Superfamily
Q#1	->Haliaeetus_leucocephalus	specific	427072	565	639	4.14E-35	127.735	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#1	->Haliaeetus_leucocephalus	specific	427072	125	199	4.27E-34	125.039	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#1	->Haliaeetus_leucocephalus	specific	427072	803	875	2.02E-32	120.031	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#1	->Haliaeetus_leucocephalus	specific	427072	348	422	9.58E-29	109.631	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#1	->Haliaeetus_leucocephalus	specific	427072	706	780	1.46E-28	109.246	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#2	->Pterocles_gutturalis	specific	427072	545	619	4.68E-35	127.735	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#2	->Pterocles_gutturalis	specific	427072	108	182	4.86E-34	124.654	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#2	->Pterocles_gutturalis	specific	427072	789	861	2.15E-32	120.031	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#2	->Pterocles_gutturalis	specific	427072	323	397	1.04E-28	109.631	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#2	->Pterocles_gutturalis	specific	427072	676	750	1.53E-28	109.246	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#3	->Aptenodytes_forsteri	specific	427072	573	647	2.38E-35	128.506	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#3	->Aptenodytes_forsteri	specific	427072	135	209	4.94E-33	121.957	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#3	->Aptenodytes_forsteri	specific	427072	795	867	8.27E-32	118.491	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#3	->Aptenodytes_forsteri	specific	427072	356	430	9.23E-29	109.631	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#3	->Aptenodytes_forsteri	specific	427072	698	772	1.40E-28	109.246	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#4	->Anstroctomus_carolinensis	specific	427072	578	652	2.00E-35	128.506	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#4	->Anstroctomus_carolinensis	specific	427072	125	199	1.83E-34	125.809	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#4	->Anstroctomus_carolinensis	specific	427072	356	430	7.63E-29	110.016	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#4	->Anstroctomus_carolinensis	specific	427072	709	783	1.18E-28	109.246	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#5	->Phasianus_colchicus	specific	427072	570	644	1.87E-35	128.891	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#5	->Phasianus_colchicus	specific	427072	125	199	9.86E-34	123.883	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#5	->Phasianus_colchicus	specific	427072	796	868	6.49E-32	118.876	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#5	->Phasianus_colchicus	specific	427072	348	422	6.83E-29	110.016	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#5	->Phasianus_colchicus	specific	427072	699	773	1.06E-28	109.631	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#6	->Camarhynchus_parvulus	specific	427072	544	618	1.48E-35	129.276	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#6	->Camarhynchus_parvulus	specific	427072	125	199	1.53E-34	126.195	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#6	->Camarhynchus_parvulus	specific	427072	788	860	1.33E-32	120.802	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#6	->Camarhynchus_parvulus	specific	427072	349	423	8.39E-29	110.016	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#6	->Camarhynchus_parvulus	specific	427072	675	749	1.30E-28	109.246	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#7	->Calypte_anna	specific	427072	571	645	1.82E-35	128.891	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#7	->Calypte_anna	specific	427072	125	199	1.35E-34	126.195	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#7	->Calypte_anna	specific	427072	799	871	1.42E-32	120.417	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#7	->Calypte_anna	specific	427072	349	423	6.66E-29	110.016	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#7	->Calypte_anna	specific	427072	702	776	1.03E-28	109.631	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#8	->Mus_musculus	specific	427072	104	178	6.36E-38	135.825	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#8	->Mus_musculus	superfamily	427072	328	402	1.28E-19	83.8227	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#8	->Mus_musculus	superfamily	405048	489	624	0.00000381518	49.151	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#8	->Mus_musculus	superfamily	436652	425	484	0.000241678	39.9418	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#9	->Camelus_dromedarius	superfamily	405048	95	172	0.00000103996	49.9214	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#10	->Bos_taurus	specific	427072	109	183	1.12E-40	143.914	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#10	->Bos_taurus	superfamily	427072	333	407	2.16E-19	83.0523	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#10	->Bos_taurus	superfamily	405048	548	625	0.00000619285	48.3806	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#10	->Bos_taurus	superfamily	436652	430	492	0.000100329	41.0974	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#11	->Mus_caroli	specific	427072	104	178	1.37E-38	137.751	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#11	->Mus_caroli	superfamily	427072	324	385	1.14E-12	63.7923	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#11	->Mus_caroli	superfamily	405048	472	607	0.000000742071	51.077	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#11	->Mus_caroli	superfamily	436652	408	467	0.00117836	38.0158	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#12	->Monodon_monoceros	specific	427072	107	181	1.13E-41	146.61	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#12	->Monodon_monoceros	superfamily	427072	331	405	2.60E-19	82.6671	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#12	->Monodon_monoceros	superfamily	405048	482	623	0.00000420518	49.151	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#12	->Monodon_monoceros	superfamily	436652	428	490	0.000116011	40.7122	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#13	->Rhinolophus_ferrumequinum	specific	427072	107	181	5.20E-42	147.381	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#13	->Rhinolophus_ferrumequinum	superfamily	427072	331	405	1.86E-19	83.0523	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#13	->Rhinolophus_ferrumequinum	superfamily	405048	492	623	0.000000813283	51.077	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#13	->Rhinolophus_ferrumequinum	superfamily	436652	428	487	0.000492084	39.1714	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#14	->Leptonychotes_weddellii	superfamily	427072	61	135	1.39E-19	83.0523	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#14	->Leptonychotes_weddellii	superfamily	405048	212	353	0.000000769223	50.8918	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#14	->Leptonychotes_weddellii	superfamily	436652	158	220	0.000252388	39.5566	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#15	->Protophthalmidius_mucrosquamatus	superfamily	405048	82	268	0.0000274819	46.0694	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	-	-
Q#15	->Protophthalmidius_mucrosquamatus	superfamily	436652	31	87	0.000495407	38.7862	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#16	->Balaenoptera_uctorostrata_sc	specific	427072	107	181	6.32E-41	144.299	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#16	->Balaenoptera_uctorostrata_sc	superfamily	427072	331	405	2.50E-19	83.0523	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#16	->Balaenoptera_uctorostrata_sc	superfamily	405048	482	623	0.00000373295	49.151	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#16	->Balaenoptera_uctorostrata_sc	superfamily	436652	428	490	0.000125499	40.7122	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#17	->Neophocaena_asiaorientalis	specific	427072	107	181	1.02E-41	146.61	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#17	->Neophocaena_asiaorientalis	superfamily	427072	331	405	2.57E-19	82.6671	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#17	->Neophocaena_asiaorientalis	superfamily	405048	490	623	0.00000623448	48.3806	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#17	->Neophocaena_asiaorientalis	superfamily	436652	428	489	0.000037859	42.253	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#18	->Neomachilus_schauinslandi	specific	427072	106	180	2.60E-42	148.536	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#18	->Neomachilus_schauinslandi	superfamily	427072	330	404	3.00E-19	82.6671	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#18	->Neomachilus_schauinslandi	superfamily	405048	481	622	0.000000374952	52.2326	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#18	->Neomachilus_schauinslandi	superfamily	436652	427	489	0.000232845	39.9418	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#19	->Meriones_unguiculatus	specific	427072	106	180	9.57E-38	135.439	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#19	->Meriones_unguiculatus	superfamily	427072	329	403	1.28E-19	83.8227	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#19	->Meriones_unguiculatus	superfamily	405048	542	625	0.000408904	42.9878	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#19	->Meriones_unguiculatus	superfamily	436652	426	485	0.00116569	38.0158	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#21	->Bos_mutus	specific	427072	109	183	1.17E-40	143.529	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#21	->Bos_mutus	superfamily	427072	333	407	2.25E-19	83.0523	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#21	->Bos_mutus	superfamily	405048	548	625	0.00000613642	48.3806	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#21	->Bos_mutus	superfamily	436652	430	492	0.0000974151	41.0974	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#22	->Pteropus_alecto	specific	427072	112	186	4.94E-39	138.906	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#22	->Pteropus_alecto	superfamily	427072	336	410	3.56E-19	82.2819	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#22	->Pteropus_alecto	superfamily	405048	487	628	0.000002801	49.5362	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#22	->Pteropus_alecto	superfamily	436652	433	495	0.0000501098	41.8678	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#23	->Ursus_maritimus	specific	427072	107	181	1.24E-41	146.61	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#23	->Ursus_maritimus	superfamily	427072	331	405	2.81E-19	82.6671	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#23	->Ursus_maritimus	superfamily	405048	482	623	0.000000117466	53.7734	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#23	->Ursus_maritimus	superfamily	436652	428	490	0.000226323	39.9418	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#24	->Manis_pentadactyla	specific	427072	107	181	1.49E-41	146.225	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#24	->Manis_pentadactyla	superfamily	427072	328	402	2.80E-19	82.6671	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#24	->Manis_pentadactyla	superfamily	405048	479	626	0.00000863483	47.9954	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#24	->Manis_pentadactyla	superfamily	436652	425	487	0.000153765	40.7122	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#25	->Varanus_komodoensis	superfamily	405048	43	131	0.000000800711	53.003	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#26	->Cricetulus_griseus	specific	427072	100	174	9.96E-37	132.358	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#26	->Cricetulus_griseus	superfamily	427072	322	396	1.65E-18	80.3559	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#26	->Cricetulus_griseus	superfamily	405048	535	618	0.00000731205	48.3806	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-

Q#26 ->Cricetulus_griseus	superfamily	436652	419	478	0.000110339	41.0974	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#27 ->Ailuropoda_melanoleuca	specific	427072	138	212	7.09E-42	147.381	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#27 ->Ailuropoda_melanoleuca	superfamily	427072	362	436	2.87E-19	82.6671	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#27 ->Ailuropoda_melanoleuca	superfamily	405048	513	654	0.000000493225	54.929	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#27 ->Ailuropoda_melanoleuca	superfamily	436652	459	521	0.000293202	39.9418	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#28 ->Rattus_rattus	specific	427072	105	179	2.63E-38	136.98	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#28 ->Rattus_rattus	superfamily	427072	329	403	1.28E-19	83.8227	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#28 ->Rattus_rattus	superfamily	405048	490	625	0.00000302373	52.6178	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#28 ->Rattus_rattus	superfamily	436652	426	485	0.00128985	40.7122	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#28 ->Rattus_rattus	superfamily	425860	260	336	0.00190389	41.0782	cl38012	ERM superfamily	NC	-
Q#29 ->Larimichthys_crocea	superfamily	405048	10	93	6.12E-10	59.1662	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#30 ->Collichthys_lucidus	superfamily	405048	134	238	0.00000426824	51.077	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#30 ->Collichthys_lucidus	superfamily	399013	500	559	0.0000012153	46.4857	cl05324	Dimer_Tnp_hAT superfamily	N	-
Q#30 ->Collichthys_lucidus	superfamily	436652	14	51	0.000960566	37.6306	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	N	-
Q#31 ->Ursus_arctos_horbililis	specific	427072	107	181	5.73E-42	147.381	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#31 ->Ursus_arctos_horbililis	superfamily	427072	331	405	3.03E-19	82.6671	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#31 ->Ursus_arctos_horbililis	superfamily	405048	482	623	0.000000245715	52.6178	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#31 ->Ursus_arctos_horbililis	superfamily	436652	428	490	0.000240072	39.9418	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#32 ->Oreochromis_niloticus	superfamily	405048	184	264	0.000234817	42.2174	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#33 ->Oryzias_latipes	superfamily	405048	63	264	0.0000000487782	57.2402	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	-	-
Q#33 ->Oryzias_latipes	superfamily	436652	33	57	0.000826629	38.0158	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	NC	-
Q#34 ->Anolis_carolinensis	superfamily	436652	16	75	0.0000121725	43.0234	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#34 ->Anolis_carolinensis	superfamily	405048	175	258	0.0000255867	46.0694	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#35 ->Odobenus_rosmarus_divergen	superfamily	405048	73	214	0.000000651846	50.6918	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#35 ->Odobenus_rosmarus_divergen	superfamily	436652	19	81	0.000363762	38.7862	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#36 ->Homo_sapiens	specific	427072	107	181	1.14E-41	146.61	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#36 ->Homo_sapiens	superfamily	427072	332	406	2.99E-20	85.3635	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#36 ->Homo_sapiens	superfamily	405048	547	630	0.0000111072	47.6102	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#36 ->Homo_sapiens	superfamily	436652	429	491	0.00100014	38.401	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#37 ->Microtus_ochrogaster	specific	427072	100	174	7.83E-35	126.965	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#37 ->Microtus_ochrogaster	superfamily	427072	324	398	2.17E-18	80.3559	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#37 ->Microtus_ochrogaster	superfamily	405048	537	620	0.0000365742	46.0694	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#37 ->Microtus_ochrogaster	superfamily	436652	421	480	0.0000963706	41.0974	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#38 ->Vicugna_pacos	specific	427072	107	181	3.94E-40	141.988	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#38 ->Vicugna_pacos	superfamily	427072	331	405	2.92E-19	82.6671	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#38 ->Vicugna_pacos	superfamily	405048	547	624	0.00000806833	51.077	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#38 ->Vicugna_pacos	superfamily	436652	428	487	0.0000323893	42.6382	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#39 ->Globicephala_melas	specific	427072	107	181	1.20E-41	146.61	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#39 ->Globicephala_melas	superfamily	427072	331	405	2.65E-19	82.6671	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#39 ->Globicephala_melas	superfamily	405048	482	623	0.00000390797	49.151	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#39 ->Globicephala_melas	superfamily	436652	428	490	0.000116011	40.7122	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#40 ->Delphinapterus_leucas	specific	427072	107	181	9.82E-42	146.61	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#40 ->Delphinapterus_leucas	superfamily	427072	305	379	2.33E-19	83.0523	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#40 ->Delphinapterus_leucas	superfamily	405048	456	597	0.00000399684	49.151	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#40 ->Delphinapterus_leucas	superfamily	436652	402	464	0.000117287	40.7122	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#41 ->Suricata_suricata	specific	427072	107	181	9.88E-42	146.61	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#41 ->Suricata_suricata	superfamily	427072	331	405	1.94E-19	83.0523	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#41 ->Suricata_suricata	superfamily	405048	546	623	0.0000108927	47.6102	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#41 ->Suricata_suricata	superfamily	436652	428	490	0.000197227	40.327	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#42 ->Nannospalax_gallii	specific	427072	106	180	1.51E-38	137.751	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#42 ->Nannospalax_gallii	superfamily	427072	342	416	1.30E-20	86.5191	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#42 ->Nannospalax_gallii	superfamily	405048	557	640	0.00000594479	48.3806	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#42 ->Nannospalax_gallii	superfamily	436652	439	498	0.000172983	40.327	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#43 ->Physeter_catodon	specific	427072	107	181	1.36E-41	146.225	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#43 ->Physeter_catodon	superfamily	427072	331	405	2.57E-19	82.6671	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#43 ->Physeter_catodon	superfamily	405048	482	629	0.0000011015	50.6918	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#43 ->Physeter_catodon	superfamily	436652	428	490	0.000559191	38.7862	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#44 ->Bos_indicus	specific	427072	109	183	7.12E-41	144.299	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#44 ->Bos_indicus	superfamily	427072	333	407	7.78E-20	84.2079	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#44 ->Bos_indicus	superfamily	405048	548	625	0.00000613642	48.3806	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#44 ->Bos_indicus	superfamily	436652	430	492	0.00010333	41.0974	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#45 ->Bison_bison_bison	specific	427072	109	183	1.07E-40	143.914	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#45 ->Bison_bison_bison	superfamily	427072	333	407	2.12E-19	83.0523	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#45 ->Bison_bison_bison	superfamily	405048	548	625	0.00000591579	48.3806	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#45 ->Bison_bison_bison	superfamily	436652	430	492	0.00010232	41.0974	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#47 ->Arvicola_amphibius	specific	427072	100	174	1.30E-36	131.973	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#47 ->Arvicola_amphibius	superfamily	427072	336	410	4.44E-18	79.2003	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#47 ->Arvicola_amphibius	superfamily	405048	549	632	0.0000897746	44.9138	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#47 ->Arvicola_amphibius	superfamily	436652	433	492	0.000116527	40.7122	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#48 ->Lynx_canadensis	specific	427072	107	181	1.62E-42	148.921	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#48 ->Lynx_canadensis	superfamily	427072	331	405	2.35E-19	83.0523	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#48 ->Lynx_canadensis	superfamily	405048	546	623	0.000146216	44.1434	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#48 ->Lynx_canadensis	superfamily	436652	428	490	0.000335351	39.5566	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#49 ->Zalophus_californianus	specific	427072	106	180	1.93E-41	145.84	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#49 ->Zalophus_californianus	superfamily	427072	330	404	3.09E-19	82.6671	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#49 ->Zalophus_californianus	superfamily	405048	481	622	0.000000177715	53.003	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#49 ->Zalophus_californianus	superfamily	436652	427	489	0.000235145	39.9418	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#50 ->Canis_lupus_dingo	specific	427072	107	181	9.32E-42	146.995	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#50 ->Canis_lupus_dingo	superfamily	427072	331	405	2.81E-19	82.6671	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#50 ->Canis_lupus_dingo	superfamily	405048	482	623	0.00000409117	49.151	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#50 ->Canis_lupus_dingo	superfamily	436652	428	490	0.000283738	39.9418	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#51 ->Orcinus_orca	specific	427072	107	181	1.14E-41	146.61	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#51 ->Orcinus_orca	superfamily	427072	331	405	2.50E-19	83.0523	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#51 ->Orcinus_orca	superfamily	405048	482	623	0.00000424389	49.151	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#51 ->Orcinus_orca	superfamily	436652	428	490	0.000116011	40.7122	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#52 ->Eumetopias_jubatus	specific	427072	106	180	1.93E-41	145.84	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#52 ->Eumetopias_jubatus	superfamily	427072	330	404	3.09E-19	82.6671	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#52 ->Eumetopias_jubatus	superfamily	405048	481	622	0.000000177715	53.003	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#52 ->Eumetopias_jubatus	superfamily	436652	427	489	0.000235145	39.9418	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#53 ->Ovis_aries	specific	427072	109	183	1.12E-40	143.914	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#53 ->Ovis_aries	superfamily	427072	333	407	1.66E-19	83.4375	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#53 ->Ovis_aries	superfamily	405048	548	625	0.00000534902	48.7658	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#53 ->Ovis_aries	superfamily	436652	430	492	0.0000200415	43.0234	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#54 ->Lagenorhynchus_obliquidens	specific	427072	107	181	1.11E-41	146.61	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#54 ->Lagenorhynchus_obliquidens	superfamily	427072	331	405	2.80E-19	82.6671	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#54 ->Lagenorhynchus_obliquidens	superfamily	405048	482	623	0.00000416683	49.151	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#54 ->Lagenorhynchus_obliquidens	superfamily	436652	428	490	0.000116011	40.7122	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#55 ->Acinonyx_jubatus	specific	427072	59	133	1.54E-42	148.921	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#55 ->Acinonyx_jubatus	superfamily	427072	283	357	2.28E-19	83.0523	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-

Q#55 ->Acinonyx jubatus	superfamily	405048	498	575	0.000149402	44.1434	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#55 ->Acinonyx jubatus	superfamily	436652	380	442	0.000263846	39.9418	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#56 ->Vulpes vulpes	specific	427072	107	181	8.71E-42	146.995	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#56 ->Vulpes vulpes	superfamily	427072	331	405	2.65E-19	82.6671	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#56 ->Vulpes vulpes	superfamily	405048	482	623	0.00000405386	49.151	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#56 ->Vulpes vulpes	superfamily	436652	428	490	0.000295118	39.9418	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#57 ->Callorhinus ursinus	specific	427072	106	180	1.82E-41	145.84	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#57 ->Callorhinus ursinus	superfamily	427072	330	404	3.03E-19	82.6671	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#57 ->Callorhinus ursinus	superfamily	405048	481	622	0.000000189568	53.003	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#57 ->Callorhinus ursinus	superfamily	436652	427	489	0.000237468	39.9418	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#58 ->Bubalus bubalis	specific	427072	109	183	1.28E-40	143.529	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#58 ->Bubalus bubalis	superfamily	427072	333	407	2.08E-19	83.0523	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#58 ->Bubalus bubalis	superfamily	405048	548	625	0.0000062498	48.3806	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#58 ->Bubalus bubalis	superfamily	436652	430	492	0.0000909408	41.0974	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#59 ->Myotis lucifugus	specific	427072	107	181	9.17E-41	143.914	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#59 ->Myotis lucifugus	superfamily	427072	310	384	5.83E-20	84.5931	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#59 ->Myotis lucifugus	superfamily	405048	525	608	0.0000110074	47.6102	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#59 ->Myotis lucifugus	superfamily	436652	407	469	0.000621096	38.7862	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#60 ->Equus caballus	specific	427072	117	191	4.43E-40	141.988	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#60 ->Equus caballus	superfamily	427072	341	415	2.95E-19	82.6671	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#60 ->Equus caballus	superfamily	405048	556	633	0.0000120816	47.6102	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#60 ->Equus caballus	superfamily	436652	438	500	0.0000479637	41.8678	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#61 ->Enhydra lutris kenyoni	specific	427072	107	181	2.72E-40	142.758	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#61 ->Enhydra lutris kenyoni	superfamily	427072	331	405	1.54E-19	83.4375	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#61 ->Enhydra lutris kenyoni	superfamily	405048	482	624	0.00000344162	49.151	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#61 ->Enhydra lutris kenyoni	superfamily	436652	428	490	0.00023798	39.9418	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#62 ->Sus scrofa	specific	427072	107	181	1.36E-41	146.225	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#62 ->Sus scrofa	superfamily	427072	331	405	2.81E-19	82.6671	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#62 ->Sus scrofa	superfamily	405048	479	623	0.00000137322	50.3066	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#62 ->Sus scrofa	superfamily	436652	428	490	0.000120662	40.7122	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#63 ->Odocoileus virginianus texanu	specific	427072	1	54	1.52E-26	103.083	pfam02946	GTF2I	N	cl08383
Q#63 ->Odocoileus virginianus texanu	superfamily	427072	204	278	2.62E-19	82.6671	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#63 ->Odocoileus virginianus texanu	superfamily	405048	419	496	0.00000620479	48.3806	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#63 ->Odocoileus virginianus texanu	superfamily	436652	301	363	0.000283891	39.5566	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#64 ->Panthera pardus	specific	427072	59	133	1.25E-42	149.307	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#64 ->Panthera pardus	superfamily	427072	283	357	2.05E-19	83.0523	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#64 ->Panthera pardus	superfamily	405048	498	575	0.000138931	44.1434	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#64 ->Panthera pardus	superfamily	436652	380	442	0.000261265	39.9418	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#65 ->Equus asinus	specific	427072	235	309	7.30E-40	141.603	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#65 ->Equus asinus	superfamily	427072	459	533	4.11E-19	82.2819	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#65 ->Equus asinus	superfamily	405048	674	751	0.0000100281	47.9954	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#65 ->Equus asinus	superfamily	436652	556	618	0.0000443585	42.253	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#66 ->Ceratotherium simum simum	specific	427072	107	181	4.00E-41	145.069	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#66 ->Ceratotherium simum simum	superfamily	427072	331	405	3.00E-19	82.6671	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#66 ->Ceratotherium simum simum	superfamily	405048	482	623	0.00000136067	50.3066	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#66 ->Ceratotherium simum simum	superfamily	436652	428	490	0.0000731075	41.4826	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#67 ->Mustela putorius furo	specific	427072	59	133	7.50E-41	144.299	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#67 ->Mustela putorius furo	superfamily	427072	283	357	1.56E-19	83.4375	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#67 ->Mustela putorius furo	superfamily	405048	434	576	0.0000251225	46.4546	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#67 ->Mustela putorius furo	superfamily	436652	380	442	0.0002025753	40.327	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#68 ->Condylura cristata	specific	427072	107	181	1.21E-39	140.832	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#68 ->Condylura cristata	superfamily	427072	331	405	2.65E-19	82.6671	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#68 ->Condylura cristata	superfamily	405048	492	623	0.00000376732	49.151	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#68 ->Condylura cristata	superfamily	436652	428	487	0.000254657	39.9418	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#69 ->Vulpes lagopus	specific	427072	107	181	8.21E-42	146.995	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#69 ->Vulpes lagopus	superfamily	427072	331	405	2.60E-19	82.6671	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#69 ->Vulpes lagopus	superfamily	405048	482	623	0.00000394394	49.151	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#69 ->Vulpes lagopus	superfamily	436652	428	490	0.000286541	39.9418	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#70 ->Mesocricetus auratus	specific	427072	100	174	8.45E-37	132.743	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#70 ->Mesocricetus auratus	superfamily	427072	322	396	1.65E-18	80.3559	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#70 ->Mesocricetus auratus	superfamily	405048	535	618	0.00000426025	49.151	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#70 ->Mesocricetus auratus	superfamily	436652	419	478	0.000112529	41.0974	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#71 ->Puma yagouaroundi	specific	427072	107	181	1.28E-42	149.307	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#71 ->Puma yagouaroundi	superfamily	427072	331	405	2.07E-19	83.0523	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#71 ->Puma yagouaroundi	superfamily	405048	546	623	0.000151625	44.1434	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#71 ->Puma yagouaroundi	superfamily	436652	428	490	0.000342011	39.5566	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#72 ->Oryx dammah	specific	427072	109	183	1.43E-40	143.529	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#72 ->Oryx dammah	superfamily	427072	333	407	2.12E-19	83.0523	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#72 ->Oryx dammah	superfamily	405048	548	625	0.00000575553	48.7658	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#72 ->Oryx dammah	superfamily	436652	430	492	0.00001799	43.0234	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#73 ->Canis lupus familiaris	specific	427072	107	181	9.32E-42	146.995	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#73 ->Canis lupus familiaris	superfamily	427072	331	405	2.81E-19	82.6671	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#73 ->Canis lupus familiaris	superfamily	405048	482	623	0.00000409117	49.151	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#73 ->Canis lupus familiaris	superfamily	436652	428	490	0.000283738	39.9418	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#74 ->Peromyscus leucopus	specific	427072	105	179	1.94E-38	137.365	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#74 ->Peromyscus leucopus	superfamily	427072	341	415	1.05E-18	81.1263	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#74 ->Peromyscus leucopus	superfamily	405048	554	631	0.0000108068	47.6102	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#74 ->Peromyscus leucopus	superfamily	436652	438	495	0.000195508	40.327	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#75 ->Onychomys torridus	specific	427072	131	205	1.21E-37	135.054	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#75 ->Onychomys torridus	superfamily	427072	355	429	2.60E-18	79.9707	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#75 ->Onychomys torridus	superfamily	405048	516	651	0.00000172751	50.3066	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#75 ->Onychomys torridus	superfamily	436652	452	511	0.00266304	37.2454	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#76 ->Halichoerus grypus	specific	427072	106	180	2.10E-42	148.536	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#76 ->Halichoerus grypus	superfamily	427072	330	404	3.21E-19	82.6671	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#76 ->Halichoerus grypus	superfamily	405048	481	622	0.000000165072	53.3882	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#76 ->Halichoerus grypus	superfamily	436652	427	489	0.000237468	39.9418	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#77 ->Mirounga leonina	specific	427072	106	180	2.02E-42	148.536	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#77 ->Mirounga leonina	superfamily	427072	330	404	3.09E-19	82.6671	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#77 ->Mirounga leonina	superfamily	405048	481	622	0.000000403621	52.2326	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#77 ->Mirounga leonina	superfamily	436652	427	489	0.000200926	40.327	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#78 ->Tursiops truncatus	specific	427072	107	181	1.10E-41	146.61	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#78 ->Tursiops truncatus	superfamily	427072	331	405	2.57E-19	82.6671	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#78 ->Tursiops truncatus	superfamily	405048	482	623	0.00000398025	49.151	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#78 ->Tursiops truncatus	superfamily	436652	428	490	0.000120662	40.7122	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#79 ->Lontra canadensis	specific	427072	107	181	6.10E-41	144.299	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383
Q#79 ->Lontra canadensis	superfamily	427072	331	405	1.39E-19	83.4375	cl08383	GTF2I superfamily	-	-
Q#79 ->Lontra canadensis	superfamily	405048	482	625	0.0000226736	46.8398	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#79 ->Lontra canadensis	superfamily	436652	428	490	0.000250237	39.9418	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#80 ->Phocoena sinus	specific	427072	107	181	1.21E-41	146.61	pfam02946	GTF2I	-	cl08383

Q#80 ->Phocoena_sinus	superfamily	427072	331	405	2.65E-19	82.6671	cl08383	GTF2l superfamily	-	-
Q#80 ->Phocoena_sinus	superfamily	405048	482	623	0.0000424389	49.151	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#80 ->Phocoena_sinus	superfamily	436652	428	490	0.000117157	40.7122	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#81 ->Phoca_vitulina	specific	427072	106	180	2.10E-42	148.536	pfam02946	GTF2l	-	cl08383
Q#81 ->Phoca_vitulina	superfamily	427072	330	404	3.21E-19	82.6671	cl08383	GTF2l superfamily	-	-
Q#81 ->Phoca_vitulina	superfamily	405048	481	622	0.00000165072	53.3882	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#81 ->Phoca_vitulina	superfamily	436652	427	489	0.000237468	39.9418	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#82 ->Mustela_erminea	specific	427072	107	181	6.84E-41	144.299	pfam02946	GTF2l	-	cl08383
Q#82 ->Mustela_erminea	superfamily	427072	331	405	1.51E-19	83.4375	cl08383	GTF2l superfamily	-	-
Q#82 ->Mustela_erminea	superfamily	405048	482	624	0.0000314487	46.4546	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#82 ->Mustela_erminea	superfamily	436652	428	490	0.00023798	39.9418	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#83 ->Capra_hircus	specific	427072	282	336	4.07E-41	145.069	pfam02946	GTF2l	-	cl08383
Q#83 ->Capra_hircus	superfamily	427072	486	560	1.39E-19	83.8227	cl08383	GTF2l superfamily	-	-
Q#83 ->Capra_hircus	superfamily	405048	647	778	0.0000112237	51.077	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#83 ->Capra_hircus	superfamily	436652	583	645	0.0000209434	43.0234	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#83 ->Capra_hircus	superfamily	223029	99	148	0.003399	41.1438	cl42984	PHA03264 superfamily	NC	-
Q#84 ->Microphorus_vespilloides	superfamily	405048	165	265	0.000676043	41.447	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#85 ->Labeo_rohita	superfamily	405048	157	240	0.000426093	45.299	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#86 ->Gadus_morhua	superfamily	436652	16	70	0.000000384566	47.2606	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#86 ->Gadus_morhua	superfamily	405048	118	255	0.0000128339	49.9214	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#87 ->Erpetichthys_calabaricus	superfamily	405048	131	255	0.0000000113178	59.1662	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#87 ->Erpetichthys_calabaricus	superfamily	399013	562	609	0.00306618	36.8557	cl05324	Dimer_Tnp_hAT superfamily	N	-
Q#88 ->Thamnophis_sirtalis	specific	426216	628	669	2.37E-20	84.7915	pfam01352	KRAB	-	cl02581
Q#88 ->Thamnophis_sirtalis	specific	227381	774	975	0.0000626933	49.6942	COG5048	COG5048	N	cl34881
Q#88 ->Thamnophis_sirtalis	superfamily	405048	169	252	0.0000977972	47.9954	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#88 ->Thamnophis_sirtalis	superfamily	436652	14	55	0.000258296	39.9418	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	C	-
Q#89 ->Maylandia_zebra	superfamily	436652	13	73	5.55E-10	55.3498	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#89 ->Maylandia_zebra	superfamily	405048	115	250	0.0000000492899	57.2402	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#89 ->Oryzcteropis_ afer_ afer	specific	427072	107	181	3.17E-37	133.899	pfam02946	GTF2l	-	cl08383
Q#90 ->Oryzcteropis_ afer_ afer	superfamily	427072	331	405	7.69E-22	89.9859	cl08383	GTF2l superfamily	-	-
Q#90 ->Oryzcteropis_ afer_ afer	superfamily	405048	546	623	0.000010598	47.6102	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#90 ->Oryzcteropis_ afer_ afer	superfamily	436652	428	490	0.000022945	43.0234	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#91 ->Lipotes_vexillifer	specific	427072	107	181	1.22E-41	146.61	pfam02946	GTF2l	-	cl08383
Q#91 ->Lipotes_vexillifer	superfamily	427072	331	405	2.47E-19	83.0523	cl08383	GTF2l superfamily	-	-
Q#91 ->Lipotes_vexillifer	superfamily	405048	482	623	0.0000275846	49.5362	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#91 ->Lipotes_vexillifer	superfamily	436652	428	490	0.00011045	41.0974	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#92 ->Chrysochloris_asiatica	specific	427072	107	181	3.17E-40	142.373	pfam02946	GTF2l	-	cl08383
Q#92 ->Chrysochloris_asiatica	superfamily	427072	331	405	3.42E-20	85.3635	cl08383	GTF2l superfamily	-	-
Q#92 ->Chrysochloris_asiatica	superfamily	405048	545	622	0.0000869922	44.9138	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#92 ->Chrysochloris_asiatica	superfamily	436652	428	490	0.00146478	37.6306	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#93 ->Elephantulus_wardii	specific	427072	244	318	3.48E-38	136.595	pfam02946	GTF2l	-	cl08383
Q#93 ->Elephantulus_wardii	superfamily	427072	468	542	1.85E-21	89.2155	cl08383	GTF2l superfamily	-	-
Q#93 ->Elephantulus_wardii	superfamily	405048	673	750	0.0000126159	47.6102	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#93 ->Elephantulus_wardii	superfamily	436652	565	627	0.000154602	40.7122	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#94 ->Rana_temporaria	superfamily	436652	16	69	0.0000209857	42.253	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#94 ->Rana_temporaria	superfamily	405048	173	254	0.000130038	43.373	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#95 ->Anguilla_anguilis	superfamily	436652	29	88	0.000000114464	48.8014	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#95 ->Anguilla_anguilis	superfamily	405048	75	271	0.000000691634	50.6918	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	-	-
Q#96 ->Periophthalmus_magnuspinnat	superfamily	405048	60	261	0.0000055875	47.9954	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	-	-
Q#96 ->Periophthalmus_magnuspinnat	superfamily	436652	14	56	0.000395208	38.7862	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	C	-
Q#97 ->Geotrypetes_seraphini	superfamily	405048	8	115	0.0000255322	48.3806	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#98 ->Xiphophorus_hellerii	superfamily	405048	31	114	0.000000672087	53.3882	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#98 ->Xiphophorus_hellerii	superfamily	399013	357	436	0.000000120188	49.1821	cl05324	Dimer_Tnp_hAT superfamily	-	-
Q#99 ->Thamnophis_elegans	specific	426216	628	669	2.09E-20	84.7915	pfam01352	KRAB	-	cl02581
Q#99 ->Thamnophis_elegans	specific	227381	923	980	0.0000094856	49.309	COG5048	COG5048	C	cl34881
Q#99 ->Thamnophis_elegans	superfamily	405048	169	252	0.0000977972	47.9954	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#99 ->Thamnophis_elegans	specific	433230	883	907	0.0000994995	40.0319	pfam13465	zf-H2C2_2	-	cl22375
Q#99 ->Thamnophis_elegans	specific	227381	867	920	0.000222268	44.6866	COG5048	COG5048	C	cl34881
Q#99 ->Thamnophis_elegans	superfamily	436652	14	55	0.000245980	39.9418	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	C	-
Q#101 ->Xiphophorus_couchianus	superfamily	436652	35	61	0.00009701	40.7122	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	NC	-
Q#101 ->Xiphophorus_couchianus	superfamily	405048	177	260	0.000143779	43.7582	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#102 ->Chelmon_rostratus	superfamily	405048	62	125	8.01E-10	59.5514	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	-	-
Q#102 ->Chelmon_rostratus	superfamily	436652	12	73	0.000000053451	52.6534	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#102 ->Chelmon_rostratus	superfamily	448965	265	395	0.00834019	37.776	cl06336	CommD superfamily	C	-
Q#103 ->Bufo_bufo	superfamily	405048	33	254	1.78E-11	64.1738	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	-	-
Q#104 ->Salvelinus_namaycush	superfamily	405048	33	254	0.00000000309656	57.6254	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	-	-
Q#105 ->Kryptolebias_marmoratus	superfamily	405048	61	257	0.0000000113029	59.1662	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	-	-
Q#105 ->Kryptolebias_marmoratus	superfamily	436652	15	74	0.00000000126472	54.1942	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#106 ->Fundulus_heteroclitus	superfamily	405048	254	335	0.0000279848	48.7658	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#106 ->Fundulus_heteroclitus	superfamily	436652	99	151	0.0000160508	42.6382	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#107 ->Oncorhynchus_kisutch	superfamily	405048	128	211	0.0000000165219	55.3142	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#108 ->Archocentrus_centrarchus	superfamily	405048	55	261	0.000000200689	52.2326	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#108 ->Archocentrus_centrarchus	superfamily	399013	567	621	0.000106556	41.0929	cl05324	Dimer_Tnp_hAT superfamily	N	-
Q#108 ->Archocentrus_centrarchus	superfamily	436652	14	55	0.000155574	39.9418	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	C	-
Q#109 ->Sphaeramia_orbicularis	superfamily	405048	180	263	0.000395708	42.2174	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#109 ->Sphaeramia_orbicularis	superfamily	399013	542	599	0.00735565	35.7001	cl05324	Dimer_Tnp_hAT superfamily	N	-
Q#110 ->Myripristis_murdjan	superfamily	405048	106	191	0.0000801967	44.1434	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#111 ->Takifugu_rubripes	superfamily	405048	64	291	0.00000000350976	57.6254	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	-	-
Q#112 ->Salmo_trutta	superfamily	405048	18	204	0.00000000165135	58.0106	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	-	-
Q#113 ->Cotoperca_gobio	superfamily	399013	399	452	0.00159404	37.2409	cl05324	Dimer_Tnp_hAT superfamily	N	-
Q#114 ->Labrus_bergylta	superfamily	405048	157	240	0.0000736176	44.5286	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#114 ->Labrus_bergylta	superfamily	436652	5	40	0.00610783	35.3194	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	NC	-
Q#115 ->Erpetichthys_calabaricus	superfamily	405048	74	267	3.90E-10	60.3218	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	-	-
Q#116 ->Podarcis_muralis	superfamily	436652	237	299	0.000000938011	49.5718	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#116 ->Podarcis_muralis	superfamily	405048	312	484	0.0000188289	46.8398	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#116 ->Podarcis_muralis	superfamily	445849	1	29	0.000057234	42.4863	cl02605	SCAN superfamily	N	-
Q#116 ->Podarcis_muralis	superfamily	445843	108	146	0.000245834	39.0698	cl02581	KRAB_A-box superfamily	-	-
Q#116 ->Podarcis_muralis	superfamily	399013	749	806	0.00257027	37.6261	cl05324	Dimer_Tnp_hAT superfamily	N	-
Q#118 ->Parambassis_ranga	superfamily	405048	99	180	0.00937634	37.595	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#119 ->Paralichthys_olivaceus	superfamily	436652	17	59	0.000000300894	46.8754	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	C	-
Q#119 ->Paralichthys_olivaceus	superfamily	405048	175	258	0.000293363	41.8322	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#120 ->Hippocampus_comes	superfamily	436652	21	80	0.0000000027717	53.4238	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#120 ->Hippocampus_comes	superfamily	405048	175	260	0.000000279335	51.8474	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#123 ->Cyprinus_carpio	superfamily	405048	153	267	0.00000327307	48.3806	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#123 ->Cyprinus_carpio	superfamily	436652	20	62	0.000198062	39.5566	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	C	-
Q#124 ->Lates_calcarifer	superfamily	405048	147	230	0.000866292	40.6766	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#127 ->malaclemys_terrapi_terrapi	superfamily	405048	19	102	0.000000060357	50.3066	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#128 ->Trachemys_scripta_elegans	superfamily	405048	35	126	0.000000021094	55.3142	cl16778	DUF4371 superfamily	-	-
Q#129 ->Xenopus_tropicalis	superfamily	436652	14	76	0.0000000251332	49.1866	cl39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-

Q#130 - >Etheostoma_spectabile	superfamily	436652	14	76	0.0000000228116	53.4238	ci39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#130 - >Etheostoma_spectabile	superfamily	405048	173	254	0.0000118632	46.8398	ci16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#131 - >Scleropages_formosus	superfamily	436652	25	87	0.000000411232	49.957	ci39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#131 - >Scleropages_formosus	superfamily	405048	184	267	0.00000132053	49.9214	ci16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#132 - >Thalassophryne_amazonica	superfamily	436652	16	72	0.00000492213	44.179	ci39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#132 - >Thalassophryne_amazonica	superfamily	405048	173	256	0.000414221	42.2174	ci16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#133 - >Syngnathus_acus	superfamily	436652	14	76	0.000000505867	49.957	ci39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#133 - >Syngnathus_acus	superfamily	405048	173	256	0.000000200809	52.2326	ci16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-
Q#134 - >Scophthalmus_maximus	superfamily	436652	14	75	1.01E-10	57.2758	ci39976	zf-C2H2_12 superfamily	-	-
Q#134 - >Scophthalmus_maximus	superfamily	405048	95	255	0.00000122574	49.9214	ci16778	DUF4371 superfamily	N	-